

Topical Meconium Improves Barrier Repair and Reduces Skin Inflammation in a Rat Model of Eczema

Anudari Ichinkhorloo¹, Khuslen Batzorig², Ganchimeg Dondov³, Batbold Batsaikhan⁴, Tsend-Ayush Damba⁵, Bolortsetseg Jamiyansuren⁵, Sodnomtsogt Lkhagvasuren²

¹Department of Cardiology, Institute of Medical Sciences, Ulaanbaatar 16081, Mongolia

²Department of Applied Neuroscience, Institute of Neuroscience and Psychology, Mongolian Academy of Sciences, Ulaanbaatar 16066, Mongolia

³Department of Oncology, Institute of Medical Sciences, Ulaanbaatar 16081, Mongolia

⁴Department of Internal Medicine, Institute of Medical Sciences, Ulaanbaatar 16081, Mongolia

⁵School of Traditional Medicine, Mongolian National University of Medical Sciences

ABSTRACT

Eczema, or atopic dermatitis, is a chronic inflammatory skin condition characterized by epidermal barrier dysfunction and immune dysregulation. While traditionally considered a waste product, meconium—the first stool of neonates—contains various bioactive compounds that may influence immune responses and epithelial integrity. This study investigates the dermatological effects of meconium in a chemically induced eczema model in Wistar rats, focusing on its potential to modulate inflammation and promote skin barrier repair. Meconium samples were collected from healthy neonates and applied topically to rats with Veet-induced eczema. The experimental groups included untreated eczema controls, meconium-treated rats, Meebo ointment-treated rats (positive control), and a healthy control group. Clinical assessments of erythema, ulceration, and edema were conducted, alongside histopathological evaluations of epidermal thickness and immune cell infiltration. Statistical analyses were performed using ANOVA with post-hoc Tukey tests. Meconium treatment significantly reduced erythema and ulceration scores compared to untreated eczema controls ($p < 0.01$) and increased epidermal thickness ($p < 0.05$). While less effective than Meebo ointment, meconium demonstrated notable anti-inflammatory and regenerative properties. The findings suggest that meconium contains bioactive components capable of modulating skin inflammation and enhancing barrier repair, warranting further investigation into its potential therapeutic applications in dermatological conditions.

KEYWORDS: atopic dermatitis, eczema, epidermal thickness, skin barrier function, topical therapy, wistar rat model

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1. INTRODUCTION

The skin serves as a vital barrier against environmental stressors, playing a crucial role in protecting the body from pathogens and maintaining homeostasis. However, disruptions to this barrier, such as in dermatological conditions like eczema, can lead to significant morbidity. Eczema, also known as atopic dermatitis, is a chronic inflammatory skin disorder characterized by erythema,

dryness, and pruritus. The pathogenesis of eczema is multifactorial, involving immune dysregulation, genetic susceptibility, and environmental factors. Studies have highlighted the role of skin barrier dysfunction and microbial imbalances in the development and exacerbation of eczema (Weidinger & Novak, 2016). More recent investigations have focused on the potential impact of microbiota and bioactive compounds on skin health, including substances naturally derived from the human body. Meconium, the first stool

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passed by newborns, contains a complex mixture of cellular debris, bile acids, and microbiota-derived metabolites. Traditionally viewed as a waste product, emerging studies indicate that meconium may have biological activity capable of influencing immune responses and epithelial integrity. Studies have demonstrated that meconium's metabolic richness is associated with immune development and may influence the risk of allergic sensitization in infants (Petersen et al., 2021). Furthermore, exposure to meconium-stained amniotic fluid has been linked to a reduced incidence of dermatitis and skin rash-related hospitalizations in offspring, suggesting a protective role in skin health (Krieger et al., 2019). Despite these findings, the potential effects of meconium on skin inflammation and barrier function remain largely unexplored. Understanding the dermatological implications of meconium could provide novel insights into endogenous factors influencing skin health and disease. This study aims to investigate the impact of meconium on skin health using an eczema model in Wistar rats. By analyzing erythema, ulceration severity, and histopathological changes following meconium application, we seek to determine its role in modulating skin inflammation and epidermal integrity. The findings from this research may provide novel insights into the dermatological effects of meconium and contribute to the broader understanding of skin barrier regulation in inflammatory conditions.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Meconium Sample Collection

Meconium samples were collected from full-term neonates within 12-48 hours postpartum. Informed consent will be obtained from the mothers prior to collection. Using sterile disposable spatulas, the first-pass meconium was gathered during routine diaper changes and transferred to a 50 mL sterile polypropylene containers. Each sample was labelled with collection date, time, and infant's birth weight. To ensure sample integrity, specimens were initially stored at -20°C for up to 7 days and subsequently at -80°C for a maximum of 3 months until further analysis. This protocol aligns with established practices for meconium collection in neonatal studies (Stinson et al., 2018).

2.2. Animal Model and Housing Conditions

A total of 12 female Wistar rats, aged six weeks, will be used for the experimental analysis. The rats will be housed under controlled environmental conditions with a temperature maintained at +21 to +25°C, relative humidity of 50% ± 10%, and a 12-hour light/dark cycle. Standard laboratory chow and sterilized drinking water were provided ad libitum. The housing conditions were designed to minimize stress and promote normal activity levels. Following a 7-day acclimatization period, the rats will be randomly divided into four groups (n=3 per group) as follows:

1. Healthy control group: Rats without eczema and treated with distilled water.
2. Negative **Control (+Veet)** group: Eczema model induced without treatment.
3. Sample group: Eczema model treated with meconium. (For clarity, this group is referred to as "**Veet+Zungag**" in the results)
4. Comparison group: Eczema model treated with Meebo ointment. (Referred to as "**Veet+Meebo**" in the results).

Animal handling and care complied with the Mongolian Standard MNS 6872:2020 and were approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC) at China Medical University.

Eczema Induction Protocol To stimulate eczema-like skin lesions, a chemical irritant method was employed. The dorsal skin of each rat was shaved, and Veet hair removal cream (Minima, LOTC05624003, Belarus) was for 30 minutes. This method, previously validated in dermatological modeling, causes chemical irritation similar to atopic dermatitis by disrupting the stratum corneum (Xie et al., 2017). After the exposure, the cream was carefully removed using distilled water and gauze.

Treatment and Monitoring Post-eczema induction, rats received their respective treatments once daily for 14 consecutive days. Skin surface changes, including erythema and ulceration, were visually documented using an intelligent detection/ hair analysis system (Hair and Scalp Analyzer, China) on Days 7 and 14. This non-invasive system enabled consistent evaluation of skin lesion severity across all groups (Fig 1).

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Figure 1. Schematic of the experimental methodology. Hair was removed and eczema was induced using Veet cream (30 minutes) on the dorsal surface. Rats were treated for 14 days in four groups: healthy control (DW), negative control (eczema+DW), sample group (eczema+meconium), and positive control (eczema + Meebo ointment). Skin Monitoring was performed using a digital scalp analyzer. H&E staining was used to evaluate histological changes. Clinical scores and epidermal thickness were statistically compared using ANOVA and Tukey post-hoc testing.

Histopathological Analysis

On Day 14, all animals were euthanized by CO₂ asphyxiation in accordance with ethical guidelines. Skin tissue samples from the dorsal area were harvested and fixed in 10% neutral-buffered formalin for 24 hours. Samples were embedded in paraffin, sectioned at 5 μ m thickness, and stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) for histological evaluation.

Key microscopic parameters analyzed included:

- Epidermal thickness
- Melanin granule
- Immune cell infiltration and dermal architecture

Histological slides were evaluated under a light microscope at 100x magnification.

2.3. Data Collection and Statistical Analysis

Clinical parameters such as erythema, ulceration, and edema were scored on a standardized dermatological scale. All

values were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Comparisons among groups were conducted using one-way ANOVA, followed by Tukey's post-hoc test to identify statistically significant differences. Graphs and visual data representations were created using standard statistical software. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3. RESULTS

Following chemical induction using Veet, all rats in the eczema model group developed notable erythema, dryness, and epidermal disruption, consistent with atopic dermatitis features (Fig 2). Within 30 minutes post-application, inflammation and skin desquamation were visibly apparent across the dorsal region in the model animals.

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Figure 2. Macroscopic images of rat skin post-eczema induction using Veet cream. Characteristic redness, inflammation, and early ulcerative lesions are visible across induced animals.

3.1. Visual and Histological Changes

Progression and treatment effects were documented on Days 7 and 14 using macroscopic imaging, dermoscopic surface analysis, and H&E-stained histological sections. Visual improvements were especially pronounced in the meconium-treated (Veet+Zungag) and Meebo-treated (Veet+Meebo)

groups. As shown in Fig 3, rats treated with meconium or Meebo ointment displayed visibly improved epidermal appearance and less inflammation compared to the untreated eczema group. By Day 14, the epidermis of treated groups exhibited marked regeneration and reduction in inflammatory infiltrate.

Figure 3. Visual monitoring and histological analysis of rat skin at Days 7 and 14 across study groups. Each row shows macroscopic skin condition (top), dermoscopic surface features (middle), and H&E-stained epidermal structure (bottom). Meconium and Meebo treatments led to substantial healing compared to the untreated eczema group.

3.2. Quantitative Analysis of Skin Condition Parameters

Statistical analysis was performed on four key indicators: erythema, ulceration, edema, and epidermal thickness. These outcomes were assessed at both Day 7 and Day 14, revealing time-dependent therapeutic effects of the applied treatments. **Erythema Score** Erythema, characterized by redness and inflammation, was significantly higher in the control group (+Veet) compared to all other groups. At both 7 and 14 days, the control group (+Veet) had the most severe erythema (4.5 ± 0.3), while the healthy (distilled water) group maintained the minimal scores (0.2 ± 0.1). Specifically, the erythema score decreased to (2.3 ± 0.4) in the Veet+Zungag group and (2.0 ± 0.2) in the Veet+Meebo group (both $p < 0.01$), compared to the control (+Veet) group.

Ulceration Score The ulceration score, which measures the severity of skin lesions, followed a similar pattern. The Control (+Veet) group exhibited the highest ulceration levels at day 7, with minimal improvement by day 14. In contrast, the treatment groups showed a significant reduction in ulceration, indicating enhanced wound healing. According to

Table 1, the ulceration score dropped from 4.8 ± 0.2 in the control (+Veet) to 1.9 ± 0.5 in the Veet+Zungag and 1.5 ± 0.3 in the Veet+Meebo groups. These results highlight the potential wound-healing properties of the treatment formulations (both $p < 0.05$).

Edema Score Edema, which reflects swelling and fluid accumulation, was most pronounced in the control (+Veet) group. The severity of edema remained high at both 7 and 14 days, suggesting prolonged inflammation in untreated skin. However, both Veet+Zungag and Veet+Meebo treatments led to a significant reduction in edema, with a marked improvement observed by day 14 ($p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.001$ compared to control). The healthy control group consistently showed the lowest edema scores, reinforcing that untreated eczema-induced skin experienced the most severe inflammatory response.

Epidermal Thickness Epidermal thickness is a key indicator of skin recovery and regeneration. The control (+Veet) group exhibited significantly thinner epidermal layers, suggesting impaired skin barrier function. As reported in Table 1,

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epidermal thickness increased from $60.2 \pm 5.1 \mu\text{m}$ in the control (+Veet) group to $95.4 \pm 3.8 \mu\text{m}$ (Veet+Zungag) and $98.7 \pm 4.1 \mu\text{m}$ (Veet+Mebo), while the healthy control group had $110.5 \pm 2.9 \mu\text{m}$. The control healthy group had the thickest epidermis, reflecting normal skin integrity. These

findings suggest that the treatment formulations aided in skin recovery by improving epidermal structure.

A summary of these findings is provided in Table 1, and visualized in the comparative bar graphs in Fig 4.

Table 1. Clinical and histological parameters at Day 14 (mean \pm SD).

Treatment group	Erythema score (day 14)	Ulceration score	Epidermal thickness (μm)
Control (+veet)	4.5 ± 0.3	4.8 ± 0.2	60.2 ± 5.1
Veet + zungag	2.3 ± 0.4 ($p < 0.01$)	1.9 ± 0.5	95.4 ± 3.8 ($p < 0.05$)
Veet + mebo	2.0 ± 0.2 ($p < 0.01$)	1.5 ± 0.3	98.7 ± 4.1 ($p < 0.05$)
Healthy	0.2 ± 0.1	0.0	110.5 ± 2.9

Figure 4. Quantitative analysis of clinical indicators at Days 7 and 14. Bar graphs display comparisons of erythema (top-left), ulceration (top-right), edema (bottom-left), and epidermal thickness (bottom-right) across all treatment groups. Significant reductions were observed in both treatment groups compared to the untreated control.

4. DISCUSSION

This study demonstrates that neonatal meconium exhibits therapeutic potential in modulating skin inflammation and enhancing barrier repair in an induced eczema model. Compared to the negative control group (Control +Veet), the meconium-treated group (Veet+Zungag) showed significantly lower erythema scores (2.3 ± 0.4 vs. 4.5 ± 0.3 ; $p < 0.01$), reduced ulceration (1.9 ± 0.5 vs. 4.8 ± 0.2), and increased epidermal thickness ($95.4 \pm 3.8 \mu\text{m}$ vs. $60.2 \pm 5.1 \mu\text{m}$). These findings suggest that meconium application

partially attenuates inflammatory responses and supports tissue regeneration.

Meconium, traditionally considered a waste product, contains various bioactive compounds, including bile acids and microbial metabolites, which may influence immune responses and epithelial integrity. Recent studies have highlighted the role of early-life microbial exposures in shaping immune development and potentially reducing allergic sensitization (Petersen et al., 2021). The presence of such bioactive components in meconium could explain the observed anti-inflammatory effects in the treated group.

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The use of Veet cream as a chemical irritant to induce eczema provided a novel approach to mimic barrier disruption, simulating conditions similar to atopic dermatitis. This method effectively disrupted the stratum corneum, creating a reliable inflammatory skin model without the need for allergens or adjuvants, aligning with previous methodologies in dermatological research (Xie et al., 2017).

While Meebo ointment demonstrated slightly superior outcomes in reducing clinical scores and improving histology, the comparable performance of meconium underscores its potential as a natural therapeutic agent. Further research is warranted to isolate and characterize the specific bioactive compounds within meconium responsible for these effects.

5. CONCLUSION

The findings of this study indicate that neonatal meconium possesses measurable anti-inflammatory and pro-repair effects in a rat model of eczema. Rats treated with meconium (Veet+Zungag) exhibited significantly reduced erythema, ulceration, and edema, alongside enhanced epidermal thickness, compared to untreated eczema controls. Although Meebo ointment outperformed meconium slightly in all parameters, the close proximity of therapeutic outcomes suggests the biological potential of meconium as a novel topical agent.

These results support the hypothesis that meconium contains bioactive molecules capable of modulating skin inflammation and promoting epidermal regeneration. As a naturally derived substance, meconium represents a promising candidate for the development of biologically inspired, pediatric-friendly dermatological treatments. Future studies should focus on identifying and characterizing the active constituents in meconium, assessing their safety in clinical-like models, and exploring potential applications in neonatal skincare or chronic inflammatory dermatoses.

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